

ROLE OF PONDS & LAKES IN WATER CRISIS MANAGEMENT FOR VADODARA CITY – A CASE STUDY

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ABSTRACT

If we take a look at the rainfall pattern of the last few years for Vadodara City, we realize that it has been very erratic. Either the rainfall is much higher than the average rainfall of the city or it is much lower than that. This has often resulted in either water supply crisis or flood like situation in the city. Even at times when the rainfall is around the normal average rainfall value of the city, there has been heavy water logging at various places in the city which was not found previously.

There are about 20 ponds and lakes in Vadodara which are scattered at various locations within the city.

These ponds and lakes, if utilized effectively / properly can play an important role in the water crisis management for the city.

This paper is a case study for Vadodara city and tries to emphasize on the role that can be played by the ponds and lakes in the water crisis management for Vadodara city.

HISTORY OF VADODARA CITY

The Vadodara city was developed by Maharaja Sayajirao Gaekwad, the erstwhile ruler of Vadodara before India obtained Independence. After independence it has been divided into four zones and 10 wards by the Vadodara Municipal Corporation for the purpose of water and waste water management. (Refer table 1 & 2 for details). It has a population of about 15 lakhs.

Table 1 Zonal Distribution

Sr. No.	Zone	Area in Sq. Km.
1	East	16.43
2	West	34.55
3	North	15.43
4	South	41.85
5	Total	108.26
6	New Additional Area	40.75
7	Total Area	149.01

Table 2 Ward-wise Distribution

Ward No.	Area in Sq. Km.
1	1.09
2	6.92
3	6.34
4	30.41
5	5.10
6	20.87
7	9.95
8	5.48
9	9.42
10	13.68
Total	108.26
New Additional Area	40.75
Total Area	149.01

The water supply to the Vadodara City comes from the Ajwa reservoir and four French wells constructed in Mahi river. There are about 23 lakes in the city located at various places scattered within the city.

RAINFALL PATTERN

The average annual rainfall for Vadodara City is around 900 mm. But there is a wide fluctuation in the rainfall pattern over the past several years. Either the rainfall is very low or much higher than the average value which results either in water scarcity or flood like situation in the city. Table 3 shows the rainfall pattern of the past 10 years.

Table 3 Rainfall pattern

Sr. No.	Year	Rainfall in mm
1	1995-1996	1004.80
2	1996-1997	1150.00
3	1997-1998	1064.00
4	1998-1999	0341.00
5	1999-2000	0398.00
6	2000-2001	0895.20
7	2001-2002	0808.30
8	2002-2003	1141.00
9	2003-2004	1146.72
10	2004-2005	1969.20

LAKES OF VADODARA CITY

There are about 23 lakes in the city located at various places scattered within the city. Table 4 shows the inventory of the lakes in Vadodara City.

Table 4 Inventory of Lakes in Vadodara City

Sr. No.	Name of the Lake	Area in hectares
1	Sursagar Lake	6.74
2	Makarpura Lake	2.24
3	Gotri Lake	1.68
4	Tarsali Lake	3.54
5	Gorwa Lake	3.53
6	Siddhanath Lake	0.48
7	Harni Lake	7.79
8	Mothnath Lake	5.39
9	Sama Lake	5.61
10	Saiyad Vasna Lake	3.58
11	Tandelja Lake	7.64
12	Warasia Lake	1.29
13	Dhobi Lake	2.41
14	Ajebdi Lake	3.79
15	Raja-Rani Lake	3.46
16	Masiya Lake	0.42
17	Danteshwar Lake	4.68
18	Ajwa Road Lake	3.41
19	Kamlanagar Lake	3.86
20	Atladra Lake	4.65
21	Lal Baug Lake	1.23
22	Manjalpur Lake	1.07
23	Mohammed Lake	0.77
	Total Area	79.26
		(About 80 hectares)

ANALYSIS

Present Scenario

If we have an overall look at the existing conditions of the lakes we can say that most of the lakes are not utilized to their actual potential. The major problem in case of all the lakes is that since no embankments are done there are slum encroachments from all sides. Even in many cases garbage is dumped by the slum dwellers. The water though not suitable but is being used for various household activities by the dwellers around. Major of these lakes pose a greater risk of being an environmental hazard to the society instead of serving as water sources.

If we look back to past most of the lakes in the old study had a proper network of storm drains. This net-work facilitated rain water to be collected and diverted to these lakes. Again most of the lakes were interconnected and finally the water diverted to river Vishwamitri which flows through the city.

But as of today, infrastructure development has resulted in narrowing down of existing natural water ways due to dumping of solid refuse including plastic bags in nallahs,

unscrupulous developments and improperly managed waste-water drains. Due to this most of the inlets are blocked, because to which the water level is not maintained in the lakes nor is the rain water diverted to the river. This has led to river Vishwamitri as just a waste-water drain all year because it hardly has fresh water flowing.

One more major problem that city is facing because of this lacking interconnectivity of the existing water bodies is large flooding. Since past two years heavy monsoon rains sparked off tremendous floods. The torrential rains were so devastating that almost the entire city was under water and all basic infrastructure facilities were jeopardized.

District Map of Vadodara

SOLUTION SUGGESTED

The average annual rainfall for Vadodara City is around 900 mm. But there is a wide fluctuation in the rainfall pattern over the past several years. Either the rainfall is very low or much higher than the average value which results either in water scarcity or flood like situation in the city.

Considering an average rainfall of around 900 mm per year and considering the area covered by the lakes which is about 80 hectares (i.e. 80×10^4 sq. m.), the approximate amount of water that can be stored in these lakes is 7,20,000 cubic metres or 720 million litres of water can be stored.

The following measures can be taken up on priority basis:

1. Revival of the old system or construction a new system interconnecting all the lakes.
2. Diversion of all the storm water of the surrounding areas to increase the quantity of water in these lakes.
3. If required, the fresh water from these lakes can be diverted to the water supply source so that a sizeable amount of water demand can be met with.

OTHER BENEFITS TARGETTED

Even if the stored water is not utilized for water supply, it can be used for several other purposes as mentioned below.

1. Even if it is stored properly in the lakes and the storm water of the surrounding areas is diverted into it, it can be a good source of ground water recharge.
2. By controlling slum encroachments and cleaning the lakes, they can be used as good recreational spaces. In case of larger lakes, boating activities can be developed which can be an additional source of income for the municipal corporation.
3. Parks and gardens can be developed around them using the water for their maintenance and development of green belt in the surrounding areas.
4. If proper cleanliness is maintained, it can be used for developing flora and fauna and improving the ecology of the lakes.
5. By providing proper lights around these lakes, they can be used for enhancing the landscape and beautification of the city.

METHODOLOGY TO BE ADOPTED

The following methodology can be adopted for proper maintenance of the lakes.

1. Proper designing of storm water drains and connecting channels.
2. Providing proper embankment or railings and pavements around the lakes.
3. Relocating or controlling slum encroachments.
4. Preventing garbage dumping and diversion of waste water into the lakes.
5. Try and create general awareness amongst the people for maintaining cleanliness of the lakes.
6. Formulating strict rules and regulations for maintaining cleanliness of the lakes.
7. Assign responsibilities for cleaning and maintenance to various government or non-government agencies.

CONCLUSION

If the above mentioned suggestions are implemented and the lakes are utilized to their optimum potential, it will help in not only enhancing the surface water sources and ground water recharge but they can also play a major role in the landscaping and beautification and maintaining the ecology of the city.

If proved successful, this can be considered as a role model and implemented for various other cities, especially those cities which are facing severe water scarcity and have large number of lakes within the city.

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